

D5.1 Visualization Prototype

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Introduction

The Big Data revolution and innovations in analytics such as machine learning, text mining offers significant opportunities to measure Research and Innovation (R&I) performance in a way that is more relevant, inclusive and open. These processes, which can collectively referred to as 'R&I analytics' are expanding the 'digital footprint' of innovative activities and providing the potential foundation for next generation R&I performance indicators such as real-time proxies that 'nowcast' policy-relevant metrics or indicators and maps for activities and sectors that have until remained underestimated or 'hidden'.

While this detail and granularity increases the usefulness and relevance of the resulting indicators, it also creates a combinatorial explosion in their number, potentially exceeding the capacity of static formats for presenting information such as reports, papers or presentations. Interactive data visualisations however, have the potential to help manage this information overload. By offering policy and decision-makers the opportunity to explore and navigate through these complex, multi-dimensional datasets, interactive visualisation tools can be used to help identify where, when, how and why innovation is happening, and how it can be supported more effectively.

In order to demonstrate the benefits and applicability of employing data visualisation as a both a research and dissemination tool in the field of innovation policy, the EURITO Consortium aims to generate, relevant, inclusive, timely and open R&I indicators, which will be communicated using interactive visualisation tools to support decision-making, encourage further exploration of novel data sources and open it up to wider audiences making R&I policy-making processes more transparent and democratic. Further, we will demonstrate how new data sources and analytical methods that capture relations between entities, such as collaboration between organisations in the innovation system, or proximity between disciplines in a knowledge map, can best be visualised as complex networks that are easier to interpret and navigate when they are presented in an interactive format.

In order to support this goal, the Consortium has developed a robust foundation of knowledge of the R&I policy landscape and have identified the evidence needs of policymakers that are poorly addressed or remain unanswered with existing data sources and indicators. This work has informed the development of 8 agile data pilots to rapidly determine the potential of different data sources and identify high potential, technically feasible ideas that can be scaled-up, validated and visualised during the next stage of the project.

In this report, we summarise the emerging findings of each of the eight pilots and provide examples of the visualisations that have been produced. We hope that this will provide the basis to support the development of a set of data visualisations and data reporting tools that allow the dissemination of the findings of the project in a way that informs action.

Pilot 1: Emerging Technology Ecosystems

This pilot uses natural language processing methods to analyse various sources of open and web data measuring levels of activity and specialisation in AI research, entrepreneurship and networking in the EU and its member states, to analyse gaps in the AI technological ecosystem in different countries, and to monitor its diffusion in different industries.

Most of the indicators developed as part of this pilot are scalar values capturing the levels of activity in AI along different dimensions (eg research activity, publications, entrepreneurship) in EU member states, as well as its level of specialisation and evolution over time. This means that most of the resulting visualisations are relatively simple. For example, the bar-chart below depicts absolute levels of activity in different territories in the top row, and relative specialisation based on a 'relative advantage index' that normalises activity in a location by its representation in the overall population of locations in the bottom row. The horizontal line in the bottom row helps to ascertain whether a territory is specialised (i.e. appears to have a comparative advantage because the relative advantage index is above one) in an activity.

The various dimensions along which we are collecting information about AI activity represent 'components' of an ecosystem which need to be in place for the successful development and deployment of this emergent technology. We have visualised these ecosystems using heat-maps where the vertical axis represents a dimensions (i.e.. data source capturing activity) and the horizontal axis represents EU member states. The colour of the cells shows whether a member state has strong levels of activity in a dimension (warmer colour) or not (cooler colours).

As in the previous chart, we display absolute levels of activity in the top row, and relative specialisation in the bottom row. This diagram helps us to visualise different configurations for ecosystems based on the presence or absence of various dimensions. We could present this information using alternative visualisation formats such as coxcomb or spider diagrams.

Another area of interest in this pilot is the level of sub-national concentration of AI R&D activity in the EU: we want to measure the extent to which activity is strongly concentrated in a small number of regions of a country, or if by contrast it is more evenly distributed. The figure below displays information with regional choropleths that display the level of activity along different dimensions of the AI ecosystem at the NUTS-2 level (in the left column), and Lorenz curves that show the share of activity accounted by various locations arranged by increasing levels of activity in AI and other benchmark variables (ie research activity outside of AI in red, and population in dashed) in the right column. This helps us to compare regional concentration of activity in AI with other relevant variables.

Pilot 2: Nowcasting BERD

This pilot began by assessing different ways in which firm-level data such as the EU Industrial R&D investment scoreboard or start-up location data from Crunchbase could be used to nowcast Business expenditure on R&D (BERD). An example visualisation that was made here is the Choropleth map below showing the spatial distribution (and its highly aggregated nature) of start-up locations contained in the Crunchbase database.

Choropleth map of start-up locations from Crunchbase.

After a firm-level nowcasting analysis was deemed to be infeasible, the pilot work pivoted to consider a more traditional nowcasting approach but with a focus on Bayesian models (particularly those with a hierarchical structure) and communicating the uncertainty of nowcasts. One such way that nowcasting uncertainty can be communicated is shown below - with Bayesian models one can sample many different predictions based on how likely the model believes they are to occur which when visualised together gives a granular view of the chance fluctuations which may occur across different sampled predictions. This also communicates the increase in uncertainty farther into the future.

Line graph communicating the prediction uncertainty of a model

Pilot 3: Technological Change Indicators

We calculate indicators of structural technological change based on ‘semantic’ discontinuities in topic co-occurrence in a variety of R&D- related data sources. We show that our approach can be used to analyse the historical evolution of the biofuel field, suggesting that this approach could be used in real time to monitor important breaks in technological trajectories suggesting the emergence of new ideas, applications or actors which might be of interest to innovation policymakers and research funders.

For the visualisation, we have used the combination of adjacency matrices and treemap diagrams to show how clusters of extracted keywords in the biofuel industry data sources change over time.

Adjacency matrix is a rectangular matrix where intersections of rows and columns signify the link between two entities. Adjacency matrix is an alternative to node-link network diagram and provides a structured and constant representation of interlinked data. Using an adjacency matrix for each year we can show how different terms are co-located with each other in the overall body of knowledge.

Treemap diagram (Johnson and Schneiderman, 1991) is graphical method that illustrates the ratios using adjacent rectangular shapes and colors. In our case, treemap diagrams illustrate how the compositions of clusters of keywords change dynamically. This allows users to see how clusters of terms (e.g. related to a certain technology) evolve over time.

Hierarchical clustering analysis of years

Changes in composition of activity

Pilot 4: Certifications based on International Management System Standards as Indicators of Organizational Innovation

Although the metadata, but no information about the diffusion, of around 20,000 ISO standards is available, we focus on the data about the certification based on the most important ISO management system standards. Every year ISO performs a survey of certifications to its most popular management system standards (see Table 1) among its more than 150 member states. The surveys reveal the number of valid certificates to ISO management system standards, e.g. as ISO 9001 and ISO 14001, reported for each country, each year and each sector. The ISO Survey counts the number of certificates issued by certification bodies, that have been accredited by members of the International Accreditation Forum (IAF). This means that these certification bodies must follow themselves a set of standardized requirements for conducting certification activities.

The more than one million certifications based on the ISO 9001 standard on quality management and the more than 300,000 certifications related to ISO 14000, the environmental management standard, provide a sound database. In order to normalize the data per country, we use the data about the number of companies in the EU Member States provided by EUROSTAT in order to calculate simple intensities. We analyse the data primarily in a descriptive way in order to show the usability of standards and related certifications as a diffusion indicator, but we will also produce heat maps by countries. Finally, we put the new indicator also in the context of the indicators used for the European Innovation Scoreboard (EC 2018).

The results of our analyses are presented according to the three dimensions time, sector and country. We illustrate the visualisations based on the ISO 9001 certificates.

Number and annual growth of ISO 9001 certificates in EU28 (Source: ISO Survey (2018), own calculations)

Numbers of ISO 9001 certificates in EU28 by sector

Source: ISO Survey (2018), own calculations

:Certification intensity related to ISO 9001 in EU28 by country

Source: ISO Survey (2018), EUROSTAT, own calculations

Pilot 5: Indicators for Mission-Oriented Innovation Policies

This pilot develops prototype indicators about the UK's grand challenge mission to "Use data, Artificial Intelligence and innovation to transform the prevention, early diagnosis and treatment of chronic diseases by 2030" with research funding data from the UK.

Most of the measures generated in this analysis are scalars capturing levels and evolution of activity in the mission field in the intersection between AI and chronic diseases, which we represent using traditional visualisations such as bar charts, line-charts and Marimekko charts (stacked bar charts normalised to the total). The latter allow us to analyse the participation of different disciplines in the mission field (see below).

We also experiment with more complex charts to display multiple dimensions of activity in the mission field simultaneously (see below). There, we represent all projects in the data in the X axis. The Y axis displays the thematic composition of each project based on a topic model of the corpus of activity. Blue topics are those which are more strongly linked to the chronic disease topic, and orange topics are those more strongly linked to AI.

In the bottom panel, we display the year where every project was funded in the Y axis, its level of funding in the size of the bubbles, and the funder in the color of the bubbles. This figure helps us visualise the evolution of the composition of the mission, as well as clusters of activity supported by different funders. This is an example of a type of visualisation that would benefit from simple interactive features such as tooltips that show the title, abstracts and organisations linked to each of the projects being displayed.

Active mission field topic mix and project characteristics

Pilot 6: Advanced Funding Analytics

This pilot uses novel scientometric methods to analyse research and development in the CORDIS database of EU funded projects. The indicators focus on two aspects of the work; attention from the research community and novelty. The first is a normalised citation index (NCI) that yields a scalar value for each project and its outputs. The second measures the evolution of a topic co-occurrence network to produce a scalar value that identifies the relative level of novelty for a research project, that we call the K Factor. While the indicator values assigned to each project are scalars, the original data contains information regarding geography, research discipline, funding levels and institution details. The indicators provide distributions of NCI and K Factor, which can be broken down by various fields, such as discipline or region.

In addition, the topic co-occurrence network that is used to generate the K Factor could be visualised to allow users to explore the connectedness between topics and identify emerging clusters of topics.

Pilot 7: Inclusive Innovation

This pilot uses a machine learning algorithm to predict gender and ethnicity of personnel in EU companies from the CrunchBase technology directory. This information is used to produce indicators of socio-demographic diversity in different countries, technology sectors and cities, also considering intersectional metrics capturing specific combinations of socio-demographic attributes. Most of the indicators generated in this pilot are scalars or proportions of activity (eg share of women in a field or country) which we represent with simple visualisations such as barcharts and stacked barcharts (see below for an example).

Pilot 8: Knowledge Flow

We map the network structure of research projects and outputs in the funding data of the funding agency in Denmark, CORDIS and OpenAIRE datasets. We generate indicators helping us understand the link between research funding and collaboration and knowledge exchange in the EU.

Basic idea behind network visualisations at the scale-up phase is to illustrate major entities in the R&I ecosystem according to various network measures, such as betweenness or eigenvector centrality, degree range and related funding amount, which could be visualised using different node sizes and colours.

While during the Pilot, we have used a network visualisation generated by Gephi software package, in the scale-up implementation phase our plan is to use more advanced and interactive visual techniques. One approach could be to use network visualisations implemented in D3.js visualisations library for Javascript.

Betweenness centrality across Horizon2020 projects

Betweenness centrality for funding agency in Denmark

As we move into the next phase of the project, we are exploring the various methods that could inform the development of the data visualisation tools. Below we have outlined some of approaches that may be considered as part of this process.

Types of Visualisations

As we move into the next phase of the project, we are exploring the various methods that could inform the development of the data visualisation tools. Below we have outlined some approaches that may be considered as part of this process.

Story-Telling

In general, story-telling approach and interactive complex visualisations should be interlinked to ease users into visualisations by providing context and cues on how to use the visualisation. One way would be to employ scrolly-telling approach, where simpler parts of results from visualisations are integrated within a narrative text that guides the user through an insight example (e.g. how standards evolve over time). Once users scroll down to the bottom of the page and have familiarised themselves with what can be extracted from the visualisation, they can find the final interactive visualisation to explore the questions that are relevant for them.

Some examples of scrolly-telling visualisations:

<https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2018/02/05/us/border-wall.html>

<https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2018/03/19/upshot/race-class-white-and-black-men.html>

Web Dashboards

Web app that show one or more often multiple visualisations, where interactions on one chart affect the [query](#) and/or the [selections](#) and hence the results, causing all the charts to update. It can use all kinds of chart, depending on the [shape of the data](#) that has to be represented in a particular area of the dashboard.

As a contrived example, the shape

```
{age: Number, weight: Number, country: String}[]
```

can be visualised with a scatter plot [age, weight] and histogram [age range, amount] to represent the distribution of ages.

By selecting certain age ranges on the histogram we can grey out or hide the points of the scatter plot that are not in the select ranges.

Interactive Maps

Interactive maps and scrolly-telling approach are combined in the visualisation of transport patterns in the city of Sydney, Australia.

<https://smashdelta.com/smartcities>

Another example of the use of maps in scrolly-telling is implemented for Washington DC, USA.

<https://districtmobility.org/stories/district-context>

Explorable networks

For explorable networks we could use force-layout or matrix visualisations to show connections between elements of a system.

Force-layout network visualisation.

<https://maxdemarzi.com/2012/02/13/visualizing-a-network-with-cypher/>

Adjacency matrix visualisation
<http://bl.ocks.org/biovisualize/raw/4541355/>

Virtual Reality

VR data visualisation, web-based (idea for scale-up 1: Mapping and Monitoring Emerging Tech in EU). Useful for offering a flexible system to explore data than can be suitable to end users (policymakers) and intermediary users (agencies/individuals working for policymakers).

Other advantages:

- multiple layers of information (multidimensional data)
- enables bottom-up exploration AND/OR top-down search
- possibility to include dashboards (including trends), together with the map or globe presented (180 Field-Of-View)
- ability to dig in the granularity of the data (regional/national)
- possibility to include layer of information from Scale-up 3 (Inclusive R/I)

Examples:

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=5&v=h3pjEjdTk8I
- <https://turf-dev.3data.io/embed.html?room=5ca2ba88209b84063ce048eb&environment=supply>

(heavy link, allow more than 10s to load)

Process

User Research

The process to identify primary and secondary user types.

Definition of User Requirements: User stories and Use cases

Here we define:

- **user stories:** the set of things the user will want to do with the application at a higher level. For example:
 - As a funder I want to analyse the volume and trends in research on social determinants of health
 - As an investor I want to analyse the volume and trends in startups working at the intersection of health and AI
- **use cases:** the set of very specific interactions the user will have with application
 - As a user I want to login
 - As a user I want to select all the items from the same continent

Definition of Technical Requirements

Based on user research and user requirements we define technical specifications. Below is a non-exhaustive list of aspects that should be considered before designing the end product(s).

Device Specifications

Platform

- Desktop:
 - Supported operating system, usually the latest 2 versions of major ones (i.e. Windows, Mac, Linux);
 - Supported browsers, usually latest 2 versions of major ones (i.e. Firefox, Safari, derivatives of Chromium – Chrome/Brave/latest Edge , Edge-pre-Chromium/IE)
 - Supported screen sizes
- Tablets (support for touch should be declared since the beginning):
 - Supported operating system: Android/iOS
 - Latest 2 versions major browsers
 - Supported screen sizes and orientations (landscape/portrait)
- Phones: support for these devices should be avoided for complex dataviz projects for various reasons:
 - The small screen size leaves no room to show more than one chart at a time and makes it difficult to interact with the fingers with maps, networks and the UI in general
 - they might have poor performances due to limited CPU and GPU power
 - They introduce concerns related with battery life

Type of connection

- can we open websockets and keep the connection alive or do we need to use HTTPS?
- What internet speed can we expect the user to have? This informs the size of the response we can safely assume the user will get without waiting too long, (for example is it reasonable to send 10k items, a json of 15MB of size, each time we interact with a slider?)

Accessibility

- it is required for all EU commission websites - see [EUROPA - Web accessibility policy](#)
- In particular we should think about impaired people (people affected by color blindness, for example) and avoid web elements like Canvas and WebGL that are like black boxes and not accessible
- OTOH, there should be a discussion about this as this would basically limit us to SVG, severing performances in the case of a lot of elements on screen – especially true for big networks where the amount of nodes and links can cause the app to lag – making Canvas and WebGL important to deliver.

Sharing technology

- Bookmarking:
 - We can use custom URLs so that the user can share a URL representing the current [data and state](#);
 - Or, we could save the current data and state on a server and let the users share an ID of the app state and data? This has implications on privacy (GDPR), costs (backend/frontend more involved logic).
- Data export: define if the user can possibly export parts of the website (images, extract of the data like CSV), also depending on the legal restrictions on the data (for example Crunchbase may limit our ability to let the user share data found in/via the app)

Others

- Define if we need authentication to save or share results or cached results or sessions
- Related to the point above, outline GDPR requirements

Design

Ideally when designing a well defined product one could outline these conceptual phases:

- concept design (ideation with sketches)
- wireframes and static visualisations for narrative line
- definition of a final UI/UX
- Development
- testing

As pilots/themes are so many and so diverse, following a rigid workflow from start to end could potentially be problematic and risky, as we might design something complex just to realise it's not the right solution.

We will then start by keeping the design at minimum for a first period, focusing on the variety of charts (trying multiple chart types for the same [data shape](#) for example) and keeping interactions to a minimum.

We will probably develop many small prototypes, as separate web apps, or as a set or [routes](#) in a single web app.

Once we'll implement and evaluate the best combination of charts to use, we will design a set of interactions and a UI for it.

By then we will also decide if the themes can fit in a single web application or not.

Development

We will write isomorphic apps, so that both the Back-end and the Client are written in javascript: this should be valid for the front-end, the charts and the VR app.

[Back-End](#)

We will need to:

- Spec the APIs to consume the collected data from DAPS
- Implement the API (probably using GraphQL)

This will be an ongoing process: we will spec and implement new APIs based on the insights we get from the prototypes.

The development will be in node, a javascript environment.

Front-End

This is the main infrastructure of the web app(s) we'll be working on.

The web app will have to be able to query the API we have developed at a certain stage and make the [Response](#) or the [Results](#) available to the current [route](#), which in turn will pass data to charts.

The chosen architecture will involve an [Xstate statechart](#) coordinating all the app events and executing side-effects (editing data, executing queries, etc) inside of its actions.

The web app framework will be [Sapper](#) which renders to the DOM using [Svelte](#). Internally, the data will be managed with Svelte's stores.

Data editing will be made using functional programming wherever it will be possible, exception being cases where we'll need imperative programming involving with data mutation for performances.

Data Visualisation

Charts will get data from the application and send events generated by user interactions back to the app.

We will use all Web APIs currently available on modern browsers if they are well supported on the [target devices](#). Some examples include: HTML, SVG, Canvas, WebGL, Audio, IndexedDB and others.

A good platform to check browser compatibility is <https://caniuse.com/> as the data presented there is based on browser testing done via BrowserStack.

We will use libraries to manipulate data and to calculate layouts for the chosen visualisations.

Where possible and when stable, functions and charts should be written as generic as possible, moved to [Svizzle](#), imported and used.

VR Application

As for the hardware, VR development will likely happen with the equipment available to Nesta, that is a HTC Vive Pro.

As for the software, again it will be a VR-compatible web app (a web page) consumed in a browser used within the VR system.

Using Unity would require coding the VR experience using a different language from the one used on the other web apps and the backend, so we will likely avoid it. All code should be isomorphic.

Testing

All APIs should be tested.

All data manipulation code should be tested ([here](#)'s an example).

Time permitting we will try to test charts too, by using headless browsers.

Tools for the Development and Branching

We will develop on one or multiple repositories, within the [EURITO GitHubOrg](#).

Ideally the high-frequency discussions will happen on Slack, and when there will be agreement on a task, this will be outlined in a Github issue.

Code will have to be reviewed and we'll follow a convention for branching and PRing.

Most likely:

- **master**: final product, will likely remain a "dead" branch until very late in the project
- **staging**: will contain developments made available to the consortium
- **dev**: will contain code reviewed in PRs
- **nn-feature-branch**: feature branch where we implement code to close a specific issue
 - The branch naming should be: <number-of-the-issue>-<free-explanatory-text>
 - We review a branch in a PR without stashing, in order to be able to review specific commits
 - When the PR has been approved and before merging the branch to dev, we [stash](#) the branch

Involving the general public on the development

We would recommend against this practise as at least for a first period we will have to keep things dynamic. To be discussed.

User Testing

Involving the general public in the testing phase will have to be discussed. We would recommend against this practise as at least for a first period we will have to keep things dynamic.

User testing from people involved in the consortium will be important, but we'll need to define some tools to facilitate the discussion. To be defined/discussed.

References

1. Johnson, B., & Shneiderman, B. (1991). *Tree-maps: A space-filling approach to the visualization of hierarchical information structures* (pp. 284-291). IEEE.

Terminology

Data shape

It is the description of the types of a certain piece of data.

For example, this data:

```
{age: [18, 24], city: ["Berlin"]}
```

Is an object with age being an array of numbers and city being a list of strings, and can be described as:

```
{age: Number[], city: String[]}
```

A list of items like

```
[  
  {name: "Annie", age: 21, city: "Berlin"},  
  {name: "Matt", age: 23, city: "Berlin"}  
]
```

can be expressed like this:

```
{name: String, age: Number, city: String}[]
```

and so on.

REST API

It is a set of endpoints, each with its own input parameters and returned [data shape](#).

For example:

```
/country/1 => {name: String, population: Number}  
/countries => {name: String, population: Number}[]
```

Back-end

It is the server responding to queries the app does from the Client.

The Client queries the Back-end using a [REST API](#).

The back-end might fetch the data it needs from another server and usually filters or transforms the data before sending it to the Client, according to the [API](#).

Query

It is an object describing what part of the whole data, available on the backend we want to retrieve: this can be expressed via forms (typing in a text input) and/or interacting with the app (clicking on a country shape on a map to select all the items in that country).

Example: "brain surgery in:europa"

Response

It is the data fetched from the backend when executing query.

It is usually in the form of a list of json objects.

Example:

```
[
  {name: "John", age: 32, city: "London"},
  {name: "Marta", age: 20, city: "Rome"},
  {name: "Annie", age: 21, city: "Berlin"},
  {name: "Matt", age: 23, city: "Berlin"},
  {name: "Mike", age: 54, city: "Berlin"}
]
```

Selections

It is the set of user selections, filters, form inputs that represents the user choice to select a part of the [Response](#).

For example, after the query has been executed, the user might select a range of age and a city:

```
{age: [18, 24], city: ["Berlin"]}
```

Results

It is set of items we have in the [Response](#) and satisfying the criteria set in the [Selections](#).

Example (following given the response and the selection above):

```
[
  {name: "Annie", age: 21, city: "Berlin"},
  {name: "Matt", age: 23, city: "Berlin"},
]
```

App Data

It represents the set of queries, user selections, and interactions with the app. For example we might select a dark theme in the app and have this app data:

```
{
  query: "brain surgery in:europa",
  selections: {
    age: [18, 24],
    city: ["Berlin"]
  },
  theme: "dark"
}
```

App state

It is the condition the app is in at any given moment.

For example right after executing a search the state of the app is "Pending", while after a request error the app would be in "Error" and after success it could be in a state we could call "Idle" or "Ready". Or, before the user has logged in, the state of the app is "Unauthorised", while after successfully logging in, it will be "Authorised". A panel might be visible (ShowingOptions) or not (HiddenOptions)

When we share the state of the application some parts of the state could be shared (like "ShowingOptions" but not others, like "Authorised", which depends on the user.

Web app routes

Different parts of a web app can be found in different paths, for example:

```
www.myapp.com/theme1
www.myapp.com/theme1/pilot1
www.myapp.com/theme1/pilot2
www.myapp.com/theme2
www.myapp.com/theme1/pilot3
www.myapp.com/theme1/pilot4
www.myapp.com/login
www.myapp.com/settings
www.myapp.com/an-experiment
```

A route is the part of the URL after the domain and can have parameters:

```
/login
/settings
/users/1
/trips/belgium?from=jan&to=dec&year=2012
```